

"RECENT ADVANCES IN ONR COMPOSITES RESEARCH"

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Research supported by the Office of Naval Research (ONR), aimed at the establishment of the scientific basis for the effective design and utilization of future composite ship structures, will be discussed. Ship structures operate in severe environments, in the presence of high humidity, sea-water, temperature extremes, hydrostatic pressure, and dynamic loading (wave loading, high sea states). In addition, Naval structures are designed to resist highly dynamic loads, including shock, blast, and implosions. Research aimed at the scientific understanding of these issues, and examples of recent research accomplishments, will be provided.